

N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) Bromination of Anisole and *p*-Substituted Anisoles in 50% Aqueous Acetic Acid

S. P. SRINIVASAN and N. S. GNANAPRAGASAM*

Department of Chemistry, Loyola College (Autonomous), Madras-600 034

Manuscript received 15 October 1982, accepted 3 August 1983

The kinetics of bromination of anisole and *p*-substituted anisoles by NBS was investigated in the presence of $\text{HClO}_4/\text{NaOAc}$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in 50% aq. HOAc. Pure NBS bromination can be followed by initial addition of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ which prevents accumulation of bromine in the system. The reaction is catalysed by AgClO_4 . Based on Hammett plot, the reaction constant is -7.85 for Ag^+ -catalysed bromination. As the water content in aq. HOAc is increased from 0-60% (v/v), the rate constant is found to increase 20 fold for PNA-NBS reaction. The product analysis of the PNA-NBS reaction catalysed by Ag^+ was done by glc which gave 2-bromo-4-nitroanisole as the only product.

LIQUID bromine is difficult and hazardous to handle. So, for the bromination of aromatic compounds a more convenient brominating agent such as N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) was thought of¹⁻³.

The kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of NBS with anisole and *p*-substituted anisoles were studied in the presence of HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in 50% aq. HOAc (v/v) at 303 K. The addition of HClO_4 was found to give reproducible kinetic data. The role of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ is to prevent any Br^- (and hence Br_2) being formed in the reaction mixture, thus enabling NBS alone to function as a brominating agent⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Liquid organic compounds (extra pure) were used after distillation. Solid organic compounds (extra pure) were used after checking their m.p.

When NBS was used, it was taken along with HClO_4 (or NaOAc) and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$. The required quantity of anisole was added and mixed well. 5 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture (50 ml) at different time intervals were pipetted out into KI to arrest the reaction. The liberated iodine was titrated against thio.

Results and Discussion

In the NBS bromination of anisole in the presence of HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ the order for NBS is one as evidenced by the linearity of the plot of $\log [\text{NBS}]$ vs t (Fig 1).

A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{anisole}]$ is linear with a slope of 1.1 indicating first order dependence on anisole (Fig. 2).

The order for HClO_4 [at constant concentration of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$] is unity as shown by the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{HClO}_4]$ (Fig. 2). Also, k_1 increased with

increasing concentration of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ at constant HClO_4 (Fig. 2). Thus, both HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ aid bromination of anisole by NBS.

Fig. 1. Bromination of anisole by NBS
[Anisole] = $2.1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.100 M$;
[NBS] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$; Temp.: 303K.
Solvent: 50% aq. HOAc.

The uv spectrum of methanol solution of anisole has maxima at 270 and 278 nm, which are not affected by the addition of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$. Hence, mercuration of anisole is not likely at the low concentration of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ used here. A methanol solution of NBS has two absorption maxima 270 and 278 nm. On addition of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ to NBS, a maximum was observed at 242 nm which may be attributed to the

complex between NBS and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (Fig. 3). This may be a σ -complex or a π -complex.

Fig. 2. Effect of varying [anisole], $[\text{HClO}_4]$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2]$ or $[\text{NaOAc}]$

$[\text{NBS}] = 2.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; Temp. : 303K.
Solvent : 50% aq. HOAc.

Fig. 3. UV spectra of NBS with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$.

- 1) $2.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ NBS in CH_3OH .
- 2) $2.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ NBS and $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in CH_3OH .

In the σ -complex, the lone pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom coordinate to Hg^{2+} . Alternatively, the π -electrons of one of the carbonyl groups form a bond with Hg^{2+} , giving rise to a π -complex. In either case, the N will become electron-deficient,

which will lead to an attraction of N-Br bond electron pair towards N, making Br slightly positive. This will facilitate the electrophilic attack of $\text{Br}^{+\delta}$ on anisole.

Effect of NaOAc in presence of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$:

The addition of NaOAc was found to steadily increase k_1 . The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{NaOAc}]$ was found to be linear with a slope of 1.1 showing the order for NaOAc to be unity (Fig. 2). In anisole-NBS reaction with added NaOAc and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$, the order for anisole was found to be zero. This suggests a slow rate-determining formation of BrOAc from NBS and NaOAc.

Mechanism of anisole-NBS reaction in presence of HClO_4 :

It is well known that H_2OBr^+ is the active brominating species in bromination of aromatic compounds by HOBr in the presence of mineral acids^{7,8}. Similarly, NBS in the presence of HClO_4 produces H_2OBr^+ . H_2OBr^+ attacks the anisole in a slow rate-determining step to form σ -complex. This in turn loses a proton in a fast step to give *p*-bromoanisole (Scheme 1).

ANISOLE-NBS REACTION (ROLE OF HClO_4)

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{K k_2 [\text{NBS}] [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] [\text{A}]}{[\text{SH}]}$$

Scheme 1

This mechanism explains the first order dependence on anisole-NBS and HClO_4 .

Mechanism in presence of NaOAc and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$:

Here, the zero order for anisole suggests a slow rate determining formation of BrOAc from NBS and NaOAc. BrOAc which is an effective electrophile^{9,10}, then attacks anisole in a fast step to give σ -complex which in turn loses a proton in a fast step (Scheme 2).

***p*-Nitroanisole (PNA)-NBS reaction :**

To evaluate substituent effect, we have investigated the bromination of *p*-substituted anisoles (since *o*-bromo compound alone will be formed). The first *p*-substituted compound to be investigated was PNA. Here also HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ were used. The linearity of the plot of $\log [\text{NBS}]$ vs t

ANISOLE-NBS REACTION (RULE OF NaOAc)

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{NBS}] [\text{NaOAc}]$$

Scheme 2

indicates that the order for NBS is one. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{PNA}]$ is linear with a slope of 0.5, indicating fractional order on PNA. Both HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ had almost no effect on the above reaction. Initial addition of succinimide [without any HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$] lowered the rate constant. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{succinimide}]$ has a negative slope (-0.7) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Effect of addition of succinimide
 $[\text{PNA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; Temp. : 303K;
 $[\text{NBS}] = 2.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; Solvent : 50% aq. HOAc.

In an earlier work¹¹, Ag^+ salts were used as catalyst in Br_2 bromination. We wanted to find out if Ag^+ salts play a catalytic role in NBS bromination also. Addition of AgClO_4 (in presence of 0.1 M HClO_4) steadily increases the observed rate

constant. A plot of k_1 vs $[\text{AgClO}_4]$ is linear (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Effect of added salts

\odot AgClO_4 \triangle NaNO_3
 \otimes NaClO_4 \square Na_2SO_4
 $[\text{PNA}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.100 \text{ M}$;
 $[\text{NBS}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; Temp. : 303K.
 Solvent : 50% aq. HOAc.

The order for AgClO_4 was found to be 0.55 from the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{AgClO}_4]$.

k_1 for PNA-NBS reaction is not affected by addition of salts such as NaNO_3 or NaClO_4 (in presence of HClO_4). Hence, the enhanced k_1 is not simply a salt effect, it must only be a catalytic effect.

The catalytic effect of AgClO_4 as well as its fractional order of 0.55 can be explained on the basis of a composite rate equation (9) as shown below

 PNA-NBS REACTION: Ag^+ CATALYSIS

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{PNA}] [\text{NBS}] + k_c [\text{PNA}] [\text{NBS}] [\text{AgClO}_4] \quad \dots (9)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} \frac{1}{[\text{NBS}]} = k_2 [\text{PNA}] + k_c [\text{PNA}] [\text{AgClO}_4] \quad \dots (10)$$

when $[\text{PNA}] \gg [\text{NBS}]$

$$k_T = k_2' + k_c' [\text{AgClO}_4] \quad \dots (11)$$

The plot of k_1 vs AgClO_4 is linear

$$k_2 = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

$$k_c = 12.8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

The equation (11) requires a linear plot of k_1 vs $[\text{AgClO}_4]$ as observed (Fig. 5). From the above plot, k_2 and k_c were evaluated as $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $12.8 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, respectively.

Mechanism of PNA-NBS reaction catalysed by $AgClO_4$:

The lone-pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom of NBS can coordinate with Ag^+ to form NBS- Ag^+ complex, which in turn attacks PNA in a slow step to form the transition state. This then decomposes to the σ -complex which quickly eliminates a proton, giving the product 2-bromo-4-nitroanisole (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Substituent effect:

Whether a carbocationic intermediate involved substituent effect was studied using PNA, *p*-fluoroanisole (PFA), *p*-chloroanisole (PCA), *p*-bromoanisole (PBA) and *p*-anisic acid (PAA) in the presence of $HClO_4$ and an added salt ($AgClO_4$, $NaNO_3$ or $NaClO_4$). The plots of $1/(a-x)$ vs t were linear indicating a total order of two.

The relative reactivities (with PNA=1) of the *p*-substituted anisoles were calculated.

RELATIVE REACTIVITIES: *p*-SUBSTITUTED ANISOL- NBS

$AgClO_4$ (0.0002 M)	1	208	381	422	1436
$NaNO_3$ (0.001 M)	1	89	141	195	364
$NaClO_4$ (0.0011 M)	1	83	106	109	181

$[ArH] = [NBS] = 0.001 M$ $[HClO_4] = 0.100 M$

Hammett equation:

A linear free-energy correlation was attempted by casting the data into an extended form of Hammett equation¹³.

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \sum_i \sigma_i^-$$

The σ_o^- value for methoxy group and σ_m^- values of the various substituents ($-NO_2, -CO_2H, -Br, -Cl, -F$) were taken from literature¹³ to calculate $\sum_i \sigma_i^-$. A plot of $\log k_2$ vs $\sum_i \sigma_i^-$ was made and found to be linear (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Substituent effect in presence of $AgClO_4$, [Substrate] = [NBS] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[HClO_4] = 0.100 M$; $[AgClO_4] = 2.2 \times 10^{-4} M$; Temp.: 303K. Solvent: 50% aq. HOAc.

From their slopes ρ values were obtained (Table 1).

TABLE 1— ρ VALUES FOR NBS BROMINATION OF ANISOL-ES

Added salt	ρ	Correlation coefficient
$AgClO_4$	-7.85	0.98
$NaClO_4$	-6.73	0.99
$NaNO_3$	-6.14	0.99

The magnitude of ρ and its negative sign suggest that the mechanism of bromination of *p*-substituted anisoles by NBS proceeds through a carbocationic intermediate.

Exner plot:

To justify the application of the Hammett equation, Exner plot^{14,15} of $\log k_2$ at 293 K vs $\log k_2$ at 303 K was drawn and it was found to be linear (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Exner plot for bromination of *p*-substituted anisoles by NBS.

This suggests that the mechanism for the NBS bromination of various *p*-substituted anisoles is similar. From the Exner plot the isokinetic temperature was found to be 404 K. This is well above our experimental temperature range (303-323 K). Hence, the observed effect of substituents is quite significant and justifies the use of Hammett equation in the present investigation.

Solvent effect :

As water content in aq. HOAc was increased from 0 to 60% (v/v) the rate constant was found to

Fig. 8. Effect of dielectric constant in PNA-NBS reaction in aq. HOAc.

$$[\text{PNA}] = [\text{NaOAc}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M};$$

$$[\text{NBS}] = [\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}.$$

increase 20 fold for PNA-NBS reaction at 303 K. Similar trends were observed at 313 and 323 K. A plot of k_1 vs D (the dielectric constant for aq. HOAc) at 303 K was found to be linear with a positive slope, indicating that k_1 increases as the D of the solvent increases. At 313 and 323 K, the solvent effect is more pronounced (Fig. 8).

Product analysis :

The product analysis of the PNA-NBS reaction in the presence of Ag^+ was done by glc and 2-bromo-4-nitroanisole was found to be the only product. It had elemental analysis, ir spectra and glc pattern similar to an authentic sample of 2-bromo-4-nitroanisole (prepared by nitration of *o*-bromoanisole¹⁶).

Conclusion :

Bromination of anisole and its *p*-substituted derivatives by NBS is a facile reaction in 50% aq. HOAc in the presence of $\text{HClO}_4/\text{NaOAc}$ along with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$. The reaction is catalysed by AgClO_4 . Based on Hammett plot, the reaction constant is found to be -7.85 for Ag^+ -catalysed bromination.

References

1. C. DJERASSI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 43, 271.
2. N. K. MATHUR and C. K. NARANG, "The Determination of Organic Compounds with N-Bromosuccinimide and Allied Reagents", Academic Press, London, 1975.
3. Arapahoe Chemicals Inc., Technical Bulletin on "Positive Bromine Compounds", Boulder, Colorado, USA, 1962.
4. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTHI and N. S. SAHU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 785.
5. V. THIAGARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron Letts.*, 1967, 3349.
6. S. SIVAKAMASUNDARI and R. GANESAN, *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics*, 1980, 12, 837.
7. W. J. WILSON and F. G. SOPER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3376.
8. P. B. D. DE LAMARE and I. C. HILTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 997.
9. P. B. D. DE LAMARE and J. C. MAXWELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4829.
10. G. C. ISRAEL, A. W. N. TUCK and F. G. SOPER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 547.
11. P. C. MYHRE, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, 14, 219.
12. JACK HINE, "Structural Effects on Equilibria in Organic Chemistry", A Wiley-Interscience publication, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1975, p. 87.
13. N. B. CHAPMAN and J. SHORTER (Ed), "Advances in Linear Free-energy Relation", Plenum Press, New York, 1972, pp. 29, 76.
14. O. EXNER, *Nature*, 1964, 201, 488.
15. O. EXNER in "Progress in Physical Organic Chemistry", (Ed.) A. S. STREITWISER, JR. and R. W. TAFT, John Wiley, New York, 1973, Vol. 10, p. 41.
16. H. T. CLARKE, "A Hand Book of Organic Analysis" Edward Arnold, London, 1920, 3rd Edn., p. 130.